

Management of Academics and Examinations: Challenges Faced by Young Lecturers during Quality Assurance Policy Implementation in Universities

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Abstract: With specific a focus on managing academics and examinations, young lecturers often face unique obstacles due to their relative inexperience and the dynamic nature of academic environments. This article explores some key challenges young lecturers face in managing their university responsibilities and evaluates how management affects staff participation. Quality assurance implementation correlates job satisfaction and young lecturers (employees') performance in academics and examination management. The emphasis on quality assurance policy implementation in universities requires participation in instruction, research and community outreach. The existing collected data has been utilized to provide empirical evidence. The article draws some data from the previous "PhD data set" from the approved study of reference UNCST ref SS-4248 where a total of 183 research participants were enrolled for the study. The study employed quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. Teaching requires preparations of teaching materials, daily research to update teaching materials, tests and quizzes, preparation of examinations, marking guides, and providing security to the examinations. At times, teaching, research and community outreach have been regarded as a heavy workload. The 40 hours for workload management, balancing teaching, research responsibilities and navigating the examination processes amid challenges of unmet benefits calls for quality assurance directorate intervention (IUCEA, 2010a). While full-time employees take 40 hours per week, several universities do not mutually compensate employees. Reciprocity in several Ugandan universities is lacking hence oscillation between several young universities in the country is associated with low salaries and insufficient incentives. The young lecturers include; early-career academics, newly appointed faculty members, junior faculty members, and postdoctoral researchers.

Keywords: Academic professional ranks, part-time lecturers, salary scale, quality assurance.

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Introduction

The academic staff are charged with ensuring high quality of university and other tertiary institutions through teaching, research and community outreach. Quality assurance policy is a new education reform policy that aims at improving quality in every high institution of learning. Quality assurance aims at reducing the defects in the products and services. Quality control and quality management are two common concepts in universities and other tertiary institutions that emphasize continuous improvement through employee engagement and commitment (Mwesigye & Kibaliwandu, 2024). The education reform policies in universities are Sino quo non since quality assurance enshrined in the Bologna

Process Accord originates from Europe. The reforms special European Union, UNESCO, UN, World Bank, and America Higher Educational institutions (Sabzalieve et al 2023). Quality assurance policy implementation compliance in Ugandan universities was ranked at 70.4% because establishing a QA directorate of quality assurance units, accountability and transparency were not yet freely acting in the country (Kibaliwandu, 2024). The workload in teaching was segregated according to employment terms and conditions. Full-time employees were assigned 24-40 contact hours in private universities. The young lecturers in public universities had a teaching workload of 16-24 contact hours per week. However, research publication and community outreach were not estimated

yet they form the three core activities that distinguish a university from any other institution of education (NCHE, 2014). The "relative inexperience" of young lecturers and the dynamic nature of academic environments, the balance of teaching and research, and navigating examination processes in universities make life complicated and undesirable.

Universities are knowledge manufacturing industries aiming at equipping the labour force with knowledge and skills. The graduates increase the availability of goods and services leading to economic growth and development (Kibairwandi & Mwesigye, 2021). Academic staff play a vital role in the facilitative teaching-learning process in universities. Teaching in universities is more challenging because of advanced technology where open resource materials (ORM) are the exposure of learners and lecturers. The third university mission must be embraced to cause economic transformation from knowledge transfer carried by technological transfer. The teacher training acquired from the university prepares teachers into professionals through courses like teaching methods, educational psychology, testing and evaluation, philosophy of education, instructional materials and teaching methods, and guidance and counselling services. However, some young lecturers do not have the teaching profession expertise to handle teaching-learning tasks. The inexperience becomes a challenge for young lecturers; early-career academics, newly appointed faculty members, junior faculty members, and postdoctoral researchers. Early-career academics are lecturers who complete their postgraduate studies and get retained at the university as teaching assistants, with promotion in academic ranks they end up becoming lecturers. Newly appointed faculty members are hired from other universities or organisations to adjust and serve as lecturers when they have not been lecturers. For example one may be an accountant in a company for some years, and he/she progressively studies for ACC, CPA, and Masters in Business Administration and gets hired to join a university as a new lecturer to serve among staff a teaching service. This may be a challenge in the management of academics and examinations. Junior faculty members hold entry-level positions as assistant professors or lecturers and are still building their teaching and research portfolios. The postdoctoral researchers transitioning to teaching roles may transit into full-time academic roles that include teaching responsibilities such as examination management among others.

Teaching is a profession because it involves specialized knowledge and skills that are acquired through professional education and training. Teaching involves content, communication and feedback. It is a scientific process where the results of the process may not be controlled by the teacher (Rajagopalan, 2019). Teaching, as a profession, is multi-faceted, involving various aspects such as content delivery, communication, and feedback. It requires a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, and the ability to communicate complex feedback that fosters learning. The statement that "teaching is a scientific endeavour where the results in the learner's head are not controlled by the teacher" reflects the dynamic and learner-centred nature of the profession. It emphasizes the idea that while teachers can guide, influence, and facilitate learning, the actual knowledge and understanding that the learner internalizes knowledge, experiences, and cognitive processes. It is also that teachers are capable of ideological orientation, enhancing thinking capacity which is sometimes known as a mediated learning experience where brain neural plasticity is at play. Neural plasticity is now well recognized as the

capacity of the human brain to be modified in its structure and function by external stimulation (Feuerstein, Falik & Feuerstein, 2013). Lecturers with knowledge and skills to ideologically orient learners on how to think, how to read, how to research, and how to manage research projects until outcomes are evidence-based will enhance the quality of desirable graduates. Teaching at university is not an "irregular" activity done through trial and error without systematic knowledge and skills. The cone of experience (Dela), the hierarchy of needs (Abraham Maslow), learning modifiability (Reuven Feuerstein) and other learning theories must be explored by trained skilful professional teachers.

The scientific nature of teaching as a science refers to the systematic use of evidence-based practices, theories of learning, and research to guide instructional decisions. The resultant effect of young lecturers teaching at university without a positive disposition is replicated when it comes to student-teachers acquiring and building up their professionalism. They see no spirit or culture of research and publication, they see a lack of professionalism, and trial and error habit of teaching in their lecturers, and they're modelled into professionals who complain of their low pay, poor working conditions, and ungrateful employees. The history of teacher training institutes; "the École Normale Supérieure ("Normal Superior School"), was established in Paris in 1794." (Normal Universities) and Jesuit Colleges were established to prepare professional teachers. While young lecturers can plan and facilitate learning experiences, the outcome, the learners' internalization of knowledge is not completely under the teacher's control. Students bring their own experiences, attitudes, and cognitive strategies to the learning processes, which influence the results. This view aligns with constructivist theories of learning, where learners actively build their understanding, rather than passively absorbing information dictated by the lecturers (Rajagopalan, 2019). Inexperienced young lecturers have misused the open resource materials (ORM) as they download and tell students to print and read. Little passes through the heads of the young lecturers' heads to the books of the students. That is from the internet to the student's books. This has often led to failure to administer examinations for the students hence several students have failed during examinations. This study, "an evaluation of staff participation explored an extensive field of quality assurance systems within Ugandan universities".

The characteristics of a teaching professional are qualities of a good teacher such as honesty, humbleness, accountability, open-mindedness, democracy, self-regulation and integrity. A profession must have responsibilities and social justice which is acquired positive disposition through specialized training and practice (Villegas, 2007). Teachers are professional in understanding child development and learning. They are vast with instructional and curriculum knowledge, and they learn and practice real teaching under the instruction and supervision of experienced teachers at the rank of a tutor lecturer or professor. Professionalism means accepting responsibilities for developing and growing one's expertise. For teachers, professionalism means acquiring and practising knowledge and skills about child growth, learning, curriculum, instruction, assessment and grading. Professional teachers follow Western formal education where a student learns and gets promoted from a low level to a high level of class attainment leading to certification in terms of academic qualifications. Therefore, this article is guided by the three objectives suggested below;

Objective

1. To explore how teaching workload, relative inexperience and dynamic nature of the academic environment affect young lecturers in managing their university responsibilities.
2. To evaluate the extent to which challenges in academics and examination management affect young lecturers' participation in quality assurance policy implementation.
3. To establish a relationship between job satisfaction and young lecturers (employees) performance in academics and examination management

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design and quantitative and qualitative approaches were applied in data collection and analysis. The survey combines quantitative and qualitative (interviewing) to provide a nuanced understanding of quality assurance policy implementation. Exploring the challenges faced by young lecturers in universities was an emerging concern established during data collection. The findings of the entire study are presented as piecemeal leading to further education reforms. A questionnaire and interview guide where 183 participants were enrolled that is 141 responded towards the questionnaire and 42 participants responded to the interview guide that was prepared for staff in administrative positions with the university. The documents on the university website and hard copies provided secondary data. The observation checklist was necessary for the researcher to establish the institutional level of compliance and validation of qualitative data. The excerpts and memos were written, transcribed, coded, verified and analysed as presented in chapter four of the main research (thesis) recorded and further interpreted based on transcribed records. The informed consent signed by the enrolled participants shows that the data set shall provide further educational information. The participants and the researcher desirably agreed that stored information can be retrieved for further research and publication in the context of quality assurance implementation.

Results and Discussion

Academic positions are listed as, teaching assistant, Assistant Lecturer, Lecturer, Senior Lecturer, Associate Professor, and Professor (NCHE, 2014). In practice, permanent workers, full-time employees, adjunct instructors, adjunct lecturers, and part-time lecturers are also service terminology detailed by appointments and contracts offered by Ugandan universities. The nature and details of appointment have left out adjunct instructors, and part-time lecturers not achieving academic professional ranks as they lack non-permanent workers status. Several university employees have retired from active service before attaining professorial ranks yet with evidence of service that would qualify them for promotion in ranks. It was established that professional ranks attract financial costs to universities. The existing terms and conditions cater for the teaching workload and leave out research and community outreach which are erroneously committed by several appointment committees. The assessment and evaluation originate from a comprehensive assembly of learners' active participation in the teaching-learning process and outside the classroom exemplary real-world experience.

The study underpins a pragmatic philosophical stance on what real-world experience and practice account for. Pragmatism uses the most appropriate methods to address existing issues where

complex social problems need multipronged approaches (Allemang, Sitte & Dimitropoulos, 2021). The policy evaluation theory has flexible and reflective generations as the researcher interacted and consulted participants with the hope of planning for the future implementation of quality assurance policy in the education system. It is accepted that governments may seek public opinion to help them in planning, reviewing and readdressing public matters of concern. Some governments have paid attention to public opinion as long as there have been governments at the same time some have neglected it. At times even the most oppressive tyrants need to know what the people are thinking, even if they just to oppress them more effectively. Organisation top management must concern themselves with the opinions of their employees and clients if they only wish to provide a basis for repression of disaffection. Policy evaluation refers to the objective and systematic examination of the effects of ongoing policies and public programs on their intended goals. It involves assessing whether policies are achieving their stated objectives and identifying impediments to their attainment (Fischer & Miller, 2017). Policy analysis is the use of formal reasoning to provide advice for solving problems encountered by governmental and nonprofit sectors, often involving the application of formal analytic techniques to predict the outcomes of different choices in the real world (Cairney, 2019). However, public policy evaluation theory has got first to fifth generations that the traditional paradigm and constructivist paradigm are where a move toward a flexible and reflective process of evaluation must be taken (Dessouky, 2016). The study was a process evaluation where university employees' participation in QA policy implementation was at work. The teaching and learning process must be considered important as staff-students semester reports of 2014, 2015, and 2016 were scanned through evaluation reports showing that some young lecturers were failing during lesson content delivery as noted by university students in Uganda (Kibalirwandi, 2024).

The policy evaluation theory is identified by several proponents such as; Daniel Stufflebeam, Michael Quinn Patton, James C. McDavid, and Peter Rossi whose works are recognized for evaluating social programs and contributing to the development of methodologies in policy evaluation (Rossi, Lipsey & Freeman, 2004). evaluation is important to review the historical background information of the policy under evaluation, its objectives and the expected outcome (Mahapoonyanont, Tharadeth & Samrit, 2012). The policy evaluation theory is a pertinent corresponding theory to study that aimed at an evaluation of staff participation in quality assurance implementation in Ugandan universities (Fischer, Miller & Sidney, 2007; Kibalirwandi, 2024). A quality assurance policy system provides a suitable working environment that enhances mutual benefits between employees and employers. Quality assurance policy implementation may yield continuous improvement and participatory engagement in sustainable production widgets and profitability returns are valued high (Reed, 1999). Therefore, young lecturers are compelled to search for extra payment from other universities in the neighbourhood hence reducing their effort committed to teaching, research and community output. The life of a university teaching staff is enshrined in research and publication where knowledge is produced to share and review. Knowledge production inspires learners to do research by taking examples from university lecturers. The 40 hours for full-time workload is distributed across the three core activities; teaching, research and community outreach.

Workload, relative inexperience and dynamic nature of the academic environment

The teaching workload for a full-time employee is expected to be 40 hours per week for teaching 14-24 contact hours, research and library 8-12 hours, and community outreach engagement 4-8 hours. The heads of department have 8-12 hours of class workload and other hours are for administrative responsibilities including meetings and consultations. The research includes students' supervision and research projects under the principal investigators or co-principal investigators where reports and publication are expected at the end of the project. Community engagement includes supervision of students on industrial attachment and community outreach activities. It was established that because of low institutional revenue from students' tuition fees private universities regard 20-24 contact hours of teaching as full-time employees, and research and community outreach engagement were not included in contracts (Kibaliwandu, 2024). The research supervision included students' research papers for the award of partial fulfilment of the ward of qualification which was not robust research to inform policy and innovation in the country (Mwesigye & Kibaliwandu, 2024).

One participant argued, "Students' research is just for training purposes on how to collect data and report, it is not serious research". Another participant said, "Universities in Uganda do not fully

fund research hence it is a waste of time to invest in research when lecturers' salary is diminutive". When considering quantitative data, it was found that 85.1% of university employees earn annual gross salary below US\$10,000 equivalent to Uganda shillings 36,000,000= it was further found that 85.1% of the employees earn less than \$3,333 annual gross salary equivalent to Ug.X11, 998,800= while 14.2% earn between \$6667-\$10,000 annual gross salary, 7.16% earn between \$10000-\$13888 annually, and only 5.7% earn above \$13,889 annually (Kibaliwandu, 2024). When interviewing top management, it was established that few employees have been promoted into professional positions like senior lecturers who earn between 11,998,800 and 15,800,000= an equivalent of \$3,333-\$4388.9 per month. The associate professor Ug. X 8,400,000 to 17,800,000= an equivalent of US\$2,333-\$4,944.44. Given the opportunity, an associate professor would earn an annual gross salary of 59,333 which is reasonable. The professor would earn Ug. X 21,000,000-27,000,000= per month US\$ 5833-\$7500 which be \$ 69996 -\$90,000= Employees in government universities were more privileged than those in private universities. The private universities' payment for credit hours ranged between 8000-30000 per hour of teaching and research supervision and was 40000 per student payable upon successful presentation of the candidate to graduation. The maximum number of students for supervision was 20 students per supervisor. This implies that private universities maximum for a young lecturer teaching 24 hours per week monthly will earn not more than 2,880,000 equivalent to US\$768= and will earn US\$7,680 for 10 monthly contracts per year. The minimum is 768,000= which makes 7,680,000= as an annual gross salary equivalent to US\$2,133.3 per year. This annual gross income does allow university lecturers to pay for research and publication in wall-pay journals.

Extra earnings to supplement the monthly salary computed for the annual gross salary in public universities were more attractive than

incentives in private universities. The examination mark allowance per script was 1500 for undergraduate students and 2500 for postgraduate students. In private universities it was not uniform, it ranges between 500-1000 for undergraduates, while graduate students marking allowance was 1000-1500 per script of examination. The private universities pay lecturers travel allows and per diem of 50,000= days outside employees' residence when in the field which may be 14 days an approximate 700,000 accommodation allowance of 700,000 and travel 1,000,000 for field or industrial supervision of the students. These allowances occur once per year. The universities have often taken lecturers as designated creatures for work who should not question issues of accountability and transparency because they work without knowledge of their rights and benefits. The human resource manual handbooks, the quality assurance institutional handbook manuals, the evening and weekend handbook manuals, the industrial and attachment off-campus policy books, and financial management and tuition fee clearance handbooks have not been fully documented for employees to access and contribute towards operationalization. Employees' salaries, allowances, and non-wage incentives take 50-80% of the university incomes in Uganda. The main source of remaining students' tuition fees for private universities. Public universities stand a better chance of funding the grants and non-condition grants are given to support 80-100% of the annual budget. The supplementary earnings from private students increase the university earnings. The private universities are supposed also to benefit from the government through state house students given that they specialise in courses that government universities have not offered entry opportunities for admission. The student loan is also an opportunity for private universities to earn huge and consolidated collections from students under the student loan scheme for science students.

The participants finally, concluded that, "I enjoy working at the university not because of high salary earned but because of the success of my students". Another participant said, "I enjoy working in the university because my participation in policy formulation, implementation and evaluation is respected by top management and administration". The existence of administrative units at the departmental level, faculty level and quality assurance directorate has increased university lecturers' engagement in the decision-making process (Kibaliwandu, 2024). While lecturers appreciate working in Ugandan universities, the need for research and publication remains costly due to wall-paid journals that demand more than \$120 equivalent to Ug. Sh.450,720 this cost almost takes a half of the monthly pay.

In Chain, university lecturers are faced with challenges such as; the lack of a unified training programme for international medical students, language barriers between lecturers and students, ineffective teaching pedagogy by lecturers, insufficient qualified and experienced academic staff and poor teaching resources, the lack of a robust quality assurance system, classroom discipline issues, and poor student quality at enrollment level stage after secondary or colleges (Jiang, Horta & Yuen, 2022). In Uganda, lecturers are faced with a lack of official appointment letters or contracts, low salary scale, delayed payment of salaries, lack of promotion in ranks, poor working conditions, lack of reference books, lack of research funds, lack of training as several courses apart from teaching professional trains teacher in instruction and curriculum including the psychology of early childhood development and learning. The obvious challenges here mentioned

are lack of appointment letters from the employer, delayed payment of salary and allowances, uncertainties which cause job insecurity, low salary scale and poor working conditions (Kibaliwandu, 2024; Mooney & O'Rourke, 2017). To overcome the challenges of teaching lesson and classroom management skills it was recommended that several employees working in Ugandan universities be offered a specialized course in educational management and post graduate diploma in teacher education. This would help university lecturers understand growth, learning development and instructional methods for children, and adults hence understanding learning processes. In universities, lecturers don't use pedagogical approaches in teaching university students but use either andragogy, heutagogy or anthropoanagogy (Kibaliwandu, Mwsigye & Maate, 2021). The science syntheses point to the following principles that provide a foundation for educators' knowledge base: The brain grows and changes throughout life in response to experiences and relationships that is the brain and development are malleable (Darling, 2022). It further accepted and proven that the pace and profile of each child's development is unique. The pathways by which children develop their skills and talents are individual and jagged, characterized by ups and downs instead of lockstep progress (Darling, 2022).

Pedagogical approaches are suitable for children under 18 years old due to its historical roots in education. The teaching of adults is known as andragogy while the teaching of self-determined adults for specific careers is known as heutogogy. Quality assurance culture encompasses the three terminologies; pedagogy, andragogy and heutagogy leading to a new educational concept (anthropoanagogy). Anthropoanagogy, the combined educational concept when it comes to tertiary education a new concept is coined to avoid polemic characteristics of each of the above-mentioned concepts. Anthropoanagogy (anthropoi referring to people and anagogy referring to inspiring (inspiration) hence inspiring people through education) is coined from two Greek words (Kibaliwandu, Mwsigye & Maate, 2020; Kibaliwandu, 2024). Teaching professional courses should be provided to university lecturers under the professional growth and development scheme for every university. It is further believed that learning is a deliberate choice of a learner set out to acquire specific knowledge and skills (Kalule, 2022).

The analysis of lecturers participating in community service had descriptive mean which was high, and workload making life work balance impossible for lecturers was high (Anariochi, 2023). The experience in Nigeria was not investigating young lecturers as it was with Kibaliwandu, 2024 yet results show that; teaching assistants contributed 14.5%, lecturers 60.1% o, senior lecturers 15.6%, Associate professors 5.1 and professors contributed 4.3% to the university staff in the country. Of these employees, 85.1% express their dissatisfaction to be earning less than \$10,000 as annual gross salary. The 14.9% are in public universities or top management offices and private Ugandan universities. The heavy workload on the employees, relative inexperience and dynamic nature of the working environment contribute to anxiety amid challenges of low salary scale to young lecturers who are not in top management responsibilities. It was revealed that administrative issues interfere with normal teaching tasks assigned to lecturers (Anariochi, 2023). In the Ugandan universities, it was found that heads of departments were given 8-12 hours for teaching, while deans were signed 6-9 hours of teaching per week. These arrangements provide a division of labour which has contributed to

quality assurance compliance at 70.4% because employees contribute to 68.5% success to policy implementation (Kibaliwandu, 2024). The results show that quality assurance is on track for universities.

Finally, workload, relative inexperience and the dynamic nature of the academic environment in Ugandan universities require the office of quality assurance directorate under the Vice Chancellor to address workload to be distributed with reciprocity, relative inexperience should be trained using on-job training and professional development. Pedagogical training may offer an opportunity for young lecturers who are not teachers by training to acquire teaching skills and knowledge (Kalule, 2022). The dynamic nature of the academic environment ranges from quality assurance policy where students are expected to evaluate the teaching process, teachers' expertise in lesson delivery and preparations, and institutional learning environment. The lecturers who may not have trained as teachers experience challenges such as being criticized by learners at the end of the semester. The competence-based curriculum in secondary schools demands that graduate teachers be taught by lecturers who know such skills and pedagogical approaches in universities. This requires university teaching approaches to be learner-centered yet resources don't allow due to lack of financial autonomy. The changing demands, diversification of provisions, changing lifelong learning, and growing information technology and computer (ICT) and need for STEM; that science, technology, engineering and mathematics (Aviwiri, 2016).

Challenges in academics and examination management

Lack of experience where university teaching requires extensive experience in course of work preparation and lesson preparation. Young lecturers often lack the experience to effectively design, and evaluate students. Fitzpatrick, Sanders, and Worthen (2004) clarified the aims of evaluation in terms of its purpose, outcome, and implication, setting of agenda, generalizability, and standards. The purpose of evaluation is to help those who hold a stake in whatever is being evaluated. The evaluation examines information like schemes of work and learning aids it considers content, formats and environment. This explains why content validity, construct validity and face validity should be considered when talking about policy evaluation. The objectives of the course must be put in mind when preparing for evaluation. The grade is provided by the evaluation while the assessment provides marks that when added together form part of the final grade and explain the evaluation. This also calls for quizzes, tests, mid-term and final examinations to provide for the grade. Stakeholders consist of many groups such as students, teachers, administrators, and staff. Poorly structured assessment and grading could bring conflicts between lecturers and students. For instance, some universities arranged their grades like; A+, A, A-, B+, B, B-, C+, C, C-, D, and F while A+, A, B+, B, C+, C, D and F as these grades would be organized, other universities had scale 4 while others had 5 as highest scale of grading. These grades and awards of assessment required harmonization by the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE). The challenge of inexperience coupled with a lack of sufficient knowledge in policy formulation and implementation remains an issue to address. The young lecturers in young universities present poor quality of service and products to the community which has often been identified that African universities have not provided quality service expected by the society (Mature, 2007). The failures in the provision of quality

education limit the achievement of the third mission of universities. The technology transfer and knowledge transfer where entrepreneurial skills are utilized in society is lacking in university graduates who are under the instruction of inexperienced young lecturers. The problem of Ugandan universities is that lecturers are faced with the challenge of lack of knowledge content (Kalule, 2022). This challenge is in private and public universities as lecturers struggle in search of knowledge content hence examination and academics face the challenge of resource books.

Administrative burden where some of the young lecturers are assigned responsibilities by their "mentors" who happen to be oscillating in other universities in search of extra earnings. This situation was also highlighted in 2010 when lecturers on transit for extra earnings were identified as "fluid" employees (Tibarimbasa, 2010). The challenge of establishing course outlines, examinations, marking guides, and entering or uploading students' grades was performed by the office of the academic registrar staff in 33.3% of the participating universities. While 50% of the university lecturers uploaded their students' grade system and 16.7% of students' grades were uploaded on the grading system by staff in the quality assurance office.

Marking student's examination scripts was centrally handled by 16.7% of participating universities while 83.3% did not have uniform methods of marking students' examination scripts. In one of the participating universities, it was reported that a young lecturer failed to return students' marked examination scripts because her child threw the scripts into the water and they were destroyed in her residence. An examination was, therefore, revised to provide a cause for a central examination marking centre for each faculty and department with facilitation in terms of breakfast, lunch and dinner for all staff members marking examinations for the particular semester. However, 83.3% of participating universities did not provide sufficient incentives for participating staff since several were poorly compensated in terms of salaries.

The new reforms in education institutions where quality assurance policy demands universities to ensure high-quality control. The process from students' admission and recruitment of lecturers to the production of qualified graduates requires transparency and accountability to provide reciprocity. Every university is expected to establish an operational office of quality assurance. The participating universities in the study found that when even these universities had sent three top leaders to Germany for policy orientation and benchmarking, 16.67% of institutions had not established a quality assurance office directorate. Also, 33.3% of the universities had no office designated for a quality assurance directorate by 2018. The public universities had no institutional quality assurance handbook formulated and approved by the university council. The private universities had several administrative working policies without the university council's minute reference for approval.

The teaching workload, where lecturers were paid at a piece rate of 8000-30,000 per hour was in private universities. The full-time workers and permanent employees were paid salaries contributing to an annual gross salary of less than \$10,000 while some 14.9%

earned high than \$10,000 per year. The low salary contributed to low morale in research and publication because per article cost was established to be \$60 -\$1200 in double-blind peer-review journals. It was discovered that in 5-10 years, several lecturers had not published except publishing with students as second or third co-authors with little of their input.

Few universities, 16.7% of the participating universities had a culture of research dissemination where every year students and lecturers could present and disseminate their research findings. The event of research dissemination attracts researchers across the globe hence increasing the opportunities for collaboration and benchmarking creating networking in research.

It was further discovered that several students whose age is still young take life easy and fail to constantly attend classes/lectures because they have nothing to lose as tuition fees are paid by parents. It was further, suggested that 50% of the tuition fee should be given as a loan from the government to be paid by the students when they join the world of employment after university education. The 50% can be parents' contribution while the student is at the university. The low tuition fee collection by private universities and little funding grants from the government frustrate university annual budget success hence impact is felt by the university employees as some even take 2-3 years before they are paid even the little mentioned salary of less than \$10,000 per year.

Quality assurance is a higher education reform policy as well as a political institution and a system that was officially declared as an education reform policy in Italy in 1999 (Reinalda, 2011). Reform is the improvement of the existing system hence quality assurance is not new but a system aiming at improving institutional structures when considering normative theory (Kibairwandi, 2024). The existing challenges in examinations and academic management will be handled when participatory decision-making strategies are supported by top university management. The professional development and growth where all lecturers are encouraged to study and qualify with a postgraduate diploma in education management. The inexperienced novice teachers, happen to create a hard time amidst low employee remunerations. The workload, unproportionate allocation of incentives, academic freedom where lecturers are not supported in work and publication

Correlation relationship between job satisfaction and Young Lecturers' performance in academics and examination management

The employees' workload, timely salary, amount of salary given in appreciation of work done, incentives and allowance for extra income, and non-wage incentives like promotion in professional academic ranks or positions cause job satisfaction (Shammout, 2022). It is accepted that a good working environment promotes high performance of employees. Working conditions, training and professional development, income and benefits, relationships with colleagues at the workplace, and organisation were identified as constructs that influence job satisfaction (Nguyen, Duy, Truong & Nguyen, 2024).

The Correlations analysis for perceived proportion items				
Control Variables			results in feedback	perceived
University Name	results in feedback	Correlation	1.000	.431**
	perceived	Correlation	.431**	1.000

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Teaching

The correlation $r^2=0.431$, the perceived variable was the job satisfaction variable while the feedback variable performance was the independent variable. This implies that feedback and job satisfaction positive correlation. The young lecturers in the university have several elements influencing job satisfaction. The results feedback contributes 0.431 while other variables contribute the remaining percentage.

The correlation analysis examines the relationship between perceived service delivery and young lecturers' performance in academic and examination management. A correlation coefficient of 0.431 at a significance level of 0.01 indicates a moderate positive correlation between these factors, meaning that as university employees' job satisfaction increases, there is a moderate likelihood that young lecturers' performance in academic and examination management also improves. Since the result is significant at the 0.01 level, we can confidently conclude that this correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance, suggesting a meaningful association between job satisfaction and lecturer performance in the areas studied. However, the moderate strength (0.431) implies that while job satisfaction influences performance, other factors may also play a substantial role in affecting young lecturers' academic and examination management outcomes.

A significant relationship between the variables above implies that lecturers have hindrances to academic performance. The researchers further inquired why performance appears low because students can read and write yet improvement is not observed. It was estimated that lecturers downloaded reading materials from the internet into learners' books without passing through lecturers' and students' heads. The Non-child Left Behind policy requires that all children be taught (Walker, 2019). The teachers were expected to be highly knowledgeable in content subject matters which is not sufficient without professional skills in transferring and sharing the knowledge. Along with professional expertise, teachers need to have the right disposition as well. Teachers' disposition and transformative leadership skills tend to complement each other in the professional duty of teaching learners in primary, secondary and university. There is a wish that learners should acquire adequate knowledge to equip them for future careers. Teachers should have appropriate dispositions to ensure they use their knowledge and skills for their students (Walker, 2019). A positive disposition is desirable for teachers in the teaching profession since teachers should be transformational leaders who enjoy seeing others succeed. There are several synonyms of disposition such as character, cheerful mood, good spirit, agreeable mood, convivial mood, temperament, temper, personality, etc. This means having an optimistic outlook and attitudes towards life, despite experiencing adversities. It is especially beneficial for staying self-motivated and achieving personal goals and career objectives.

Conclusion

The university governance and management have failed to harmonize employees' engagement in the three core activities; teaching, research and community outreach. The heavy workload, low rate of research productivity, insufficient supervision of student's research projects and industrial attachment are manifestations of resistance to change or lack of sufficient knowledge in quality assurance policy implementation. The 40 hours per week input workload should be distributed among the three core activities, relative inexperience lecturers should be given

on-job credited hour transferable credits leading to professionalism. The dynamic nature of the academic environment affects young lecturers in managing their university responsibilities should be enhanced to people friendly environment.

Education reform policies should be participatory at the policy formulation stage. The extent to which challenges in academics and examination management affect young lecturers' participation in quality assurance policy implementation. Reciprocity is dearly needed to enhance employees' engagement in policy formulation, implementation and review for evaluation. The challenge of knowledge content can be addressed by lecturers organising and publishing their reading materials published by the universities into journal booklets and handouts.

The employees are delegated staff for the employer who provides service to institutional clients. The employees in the manufacturing industry are the customers/consumers of the produced products. It was

found that the quality of a product has a significant impact on the customer's satisfaction, and in turn, leads to high performance/efficiency of manufacturing companies. Research show that there is a significant relationship between product quality and customers satisfaction. the customers are capable of evaluating and recommending the quality of the product for consumption. The participants 'perceived service delivery was equivalent to their job satisfaction. Therefore, establishing a relationship between job satisfaction and young lecturers (employees') performance in academics and examination management is significantly observed when identifying compliance at 70.4% and staff participation towards successful policy implementation to be at 68.5% and other variables accounting for the remaining percentage.

Recommendations

University employees' workload of 40 hours per week for full-time employees should distributed across the three core activities. The contract or appointment should be clear in white and black for each time allocation. The compensation should be enhanced based on each invested time into the three core activities.

The employee's engagement at different administrative levels should be enhanced by involving stakeholders since knowledge of the policy process is important for policy implementation. The on-job credit training for university staff since teaching is a scientific professional where lecturers work with the brain modifiability of learners through scientific experiments.

The employees are both delegated members representing the employer and need to be empowered by signed legal contracts. They ought to be equipped with the right message to the institutional clients who are students, parents and sponsors, the private sector who is the largest employer, and the government.

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